

Correlation between Structure and Crystallization of Porphyrins and Derivatives

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ABSTRACT

In this study we have analysed some parameters that may affect crystal quality and lead to an optimal crystallization of porphyrins and derivatives structures. We used experimental data from Cambridge Structural Database (CSD), which we correlated geometric and chemical parameters of crystals molecular structures to the refinement parameter (R) assessed during the crystallographic three dimensional (3D) structures resolution by single crystal X-ray diffraction. Based on 3D visualization of a relatively large sample of structures, the obtained results indicate that porphyrins that gave good crystals are those structures are strongly deformed as an occurrence of the meso carbons substitution or of the metal atom insertion in the central cavity bound to four nitrogen atoms of the nucleus. The unit cells of such crystals do not have voids or in the cases of having voids, need to be packed by solvents molecules used during crystallization process. Out of the usually studied parameters in order to understand the easiest ability of crystallizing of biological molecules, the parameters like geometric and chemical structures of porphyrins, solvents, and derivatives may be taken into account in order to predict the expected quality of crystals and the reliability of the method that we have to choose for their easiest crystallization.

Keywords: Porphyrins and derivatives, Crystal's structure, Crystallization, Refinement factor,

INTRODUCTION

Porphyrins have earned the title “pigments of life” because their essential character for all life on planet earth. Porphyrins are the precursors of heme, chlorophyll, and cyanocobalamin (vitamin B12). Heme is an iron-coordinated porphyrin and serves as a prosthetic group in several proteins to mediate catalysis (cytochromes, peroxidases) or recognize diatomic molecules like oxygen (globins), carbon monoxide (CO) (cytochrome oxidase), and nitric oxide (NO) (soluble guanylyl cyclase) [1-3]. They have mostly aroused remarkable and extensive interest for many years due to their wideranging applications in photophysics, coordination chemistry, liquid crystals, solar cells, catalysis, photovoltaic devices, photodynamic therapy (PDT) and artificial light harvesting antennas thanks to their strong absorption in the visible and the photosensitizing property [4-6]. During the last few years under their simple shape, porphyrins and metalloporphyrins have also attracted widespread attention as chromophores for studies in circular dichroism (CD), an indispensable chiroptical tool for monitoring chiral interactions [7-9]. In medicinal chemistry they have been utilized for the development of artificial receptors for molecular recognition and new chiral catalysts for asymmetric synthesis, so that to explore the mechanisms of biologically important reactions such as photosynthesis and P450-catalyzed redox reactions, and for the study of stereochemistry [10, 11]. Molecular recognition is a fundamental process for a range of chemical and biological phenomena as for that group of structures. The biological activity of antimalarial drugs based-quinoline nucleus, the most used drugs to heal the disease was attributed to heme which acts as receptor. Indeed it was demonstrated that the complex formed by heme and quinoline nucleus of antimalarial drugs is toxic to *plasmodium falciparum* and leads to its eliminating in the infected erythrocytes [12, 13]. So many studies are interested to underline the interaction

heme-quinoline and to elucidate the 3D structure of complexes formed so that to solve the chemical major problem of drugs-resistance developed by the *plasmodium* to the most efficient drugs currently used, and that activities of existing molecular structures may be improved during the design of new effective drugs [14,15]. Crystals structure especially have become so popular [16-18], but the 3D structures elucidation of heme-quinoline complex did not progress in despite of the high precision and great reliability that supply the single crystal X-ray diffraction, the powerful used method. A single crystal is required in the structure resolution by the x-ray diffraction technique. Such “crystal engineering” promises to shift our understanding of the formation of solid-state structures from a process of empirical self-assembly to a rational consideration of component shape, the summation of weak intermolecular forces, and the dynamics of crystal growth [19]. The ideal size of crystals required is generally estimated to 0.5 mm. Crystal quality governs the quality of results obtained [20]. That can explain the rarity of results in the study of heme-quinoline interaction. Indeed, few results have been yielded [21]. Suk Joong Lee *et al.*, have shown that secondary substituents Sn-porphyrins have effects on the physical properties, crystal structures, and nanoparticle morphologies [22]. Bhyrappa P and Arunkumar C have also noticed that non-planar distortion of Cu- and Zn-porphyrins ring in the crystals structure [23]. But there are no results that link the observed effects to parameters of crystallization. Considering their importance as biological and technological molecular materials, understanding the background of the crystallization of porphyrins and derivatives structures in general, especially those containing iron as central atom is a great purpose of scientific research. The goal of this work was to correlate known experimental structural data to the refinement parameters R assessed during the three dimensional (3D)

crystallographic structures resolution by X-ray diffraction from single crystals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Computational

The CSD is the world's repository for small-molecule organic and metal-organic crystal structures. Containing the results of over half-a-million x-ray and neutron diffraction analysis. This unique database of accurate 3D structures has become an essential resource to scientists around the world [24]. Each CSD entry contains the following information (fully described elsewhere): Bibliographic, textual, and numerical information, Chemical diagram, Crystal structure data, Filters (secondary search criteria). The figure 1 summarizes the nature of experimental data that supply CSD software.

Figure 1: Cambridge Structural Database informations CSD [24, 25].

Each CSD entry is identified by a unique refcode (entry ID) comprising: Six letters, e.g. ABACOF, Two digits identifying additional structure determinations, e.g. ABACOF03. The CSD also records a variety of deposition numbers published by many primary journals to identify crystallographic data deposited with the CCDC [26].

The study is semi-empirical (i.e. we use computational tools and study experimental data) and appeal to softwares, especially ConQuest, Mercury and Vista, developed by Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC) for the handling of Cambridge Structural Database. The 2015 release of the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD version 5.36) containing a total of 717,876 entries was used. ConQuest is firstly used to search all the sample of porphyrins and derivatives structures by defining geometric and chemical parameters such as: refinement parameter R, substitutions, chemical bonds, angles, torsions, plans, unit cells, etc. and secondly to send the structures and data found on CSD to Mercury, the most developed CSD software to calculate and visualizing 3D structures with their crystallographic parameters. The numerical data from CSD are also sent to Vista a CSD statistical data analysis software, where statistical calculations and graphics are made. In each case, all structural data related to the sample of porphyrins and derivatives from CSD are correlated in order to show the relative importance of each parameter on the refinement parameters.

Porphyrins structure

The general structure of a porphyrin cycle is shown in the figure 2 and is numbered according to the UPAC nomenclature. Porphyrin is an aromatic macrocyclic tetrapyrrole [27], which is characterized by three kinds of carbon atoms α , β and meso. Four fused pyrrole molecules, are attached by methenes (=CH—) considered as meso carbons (5, 10, 15 and 20). The two carbons of each pyrrole cycles attached to nitrogen atom which bind to the meso carbons are named α (1, 4, 6, 9, 11, 14, 16 and 19) and the remaining external carbons of each pyrrole cycles are named β (2, 3, 7, 8, 12, 13, 17 and 18). In non metallic porphyrins two pyrroles carry on hydrogen atom as for β carbons atoms in unsubstituted cases [28, 29].

Figure 2: Molecular structure of a porphyrin and its nomenclature. The occurring of large substitutes around porphyrins and derivatives such as phenyles in meso positions lead to the losing of their planar structures and becoming nonplanar. The nonplanar conformation occurs to limit steric interactions of substitutes with β -pyrrolic hydrogens [23]. The four resulting different conformational possibility are shown in the figure 3. Protonation of the two non hydrogenated nitrogens, the presence of axial ligands in the case of metallic porphyrins and the environment of the aromatic macrocyclic tetrapyrrole can also be responsible of the occurring of nonplanar conformations [30, 31].

Figure 3: Conformational possibility of porphyrins and derivatives

Refinement Parameter

Crystals quality governs reliability of results obtained i.e. the precision of the structure was determined [20]. The refinement parameter is introduced as the essential criterion to estimating the precision of the 3D structure solved by single crystal X-ray diffraction.

$$R = \frac{\sum_H \|F_0\| - |F_C|}{\sum_H |F_0|}$$

Where F_0 and F_C correspond to experimental and calculated factors of structure, respectively. And are calculated by:

$$F_{hkl} = \int_x \int_y \int_z \rho(X, Y, Z) \exp[2\pi i(hx + ky + lz)] dx dy dz$$

Which is the Fourier transformed of the electronic density of all atoms in the units cells given by:

$$\rho(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{V} \sum_h \sum_k \sum_l F_{hkl} \exp[-2\pi i(hx + ky + lz)]$$

Where: (x, y, z) : Position of each atom into the unit cell, V :

Volume of the unit cell, (hkl) : reflexion plans of X-ray beam in the unit cell

The factor of structure F_{hkl} is the amplitude of diffusion of X-ray in the unit cell and each unit cell intervenes in the diffusion of the crystal. So the accurate accepted values during structure resolution are those of $R < 0.1$ or 10% The relative qualities of structures are, R : 1 – 3% : Exceptional, 3 – 4% : Very high, 4 – 5% : High, 5 – 7% : Good, 7 – 9% : Mean, 9 – 10% : Enough, 10 – 15% : Poor, > 0.15 Wrong [32].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of 717,876 crystalline structures solved by single crystal X-ray diffraction permitted to list a total of 5794 structures of porphyrins and derivatives or 0.81% entry. We can notice the relatively weak rate of porphyrins structures and their corresponding derivatives.

Refinement parameter R analysis

The figure 4 shows the histogram of distributions of different structures of porphyrins versus their refinement parameters.

Figure 4: Distribution of different porphyrins and derivatives versus R.

It can be noticed that the mean of the refinement parameter of porphyrins structures in CSD is $R = 6.682 \pm 2.848$ %, i.e. all those structures have been solved with $3.843 < R < 9.53$; indicating the high, good and medium precision with which most of structures were solved. But in the figure 4, we can see the presence of some structures less accurate occurring with $10 < R < 44.2$. The analysis of the refinement parameter also indicates that 89% of porphyrins structures of CSD have been solved with $R \leq 10\%$. The distribution of such structures with $R \leq 10\%$ is showed in the figure 5, in order to get rid of less accurate structures locating $R > 10\%$.

Figure 5: Distribution of different porphyrins versus R ($R \leq 10\%$). All those porphyrins structures have been determined with very high, high and good precision. The mean value of the refinement parameter is $R = 6.191 \pm 1.806$ %, so, all the the structures are characterized with $4.385 < R < 7.779$, showing the reliability of 89% of CSD porphyrins structures.

Packing analysis

The analysis of the unit cells revealed various structures packing. The figure 6 shows five examples of packing. Unit cells are more or less packed and were characterized in three groups. The first that is highly packed, and includes few solvents molecules that cover the small voids of the unit cells (figure 6 a-b), the second that is moderately packed includes many solvents molecules that cover the voids (figure 6 c) and the last group that have a low packing do not have enough solvents molecules (figure 6 d-e). In the case of high packing, the voids spaces of unit cells are completely cover by solvents molecules used during crystallization, while in the case of moderately packing unit cells, there not enough solvents molecules to cover all the voids spaces.

(a) ALIZOK (b) ATIMOF (c) ATIMEV (d) ATIREA (e) BOHQIY

Figure 6: 3D visualization of packing.

We have noticed that there is reverse correlation between packing of unit cells and the refinement parameters R. It has been notice that high packing of porphyrins and derivatives structures occur with $R \leq 5\%$, while low packing correspond to $R > 5\%$. This correlation shows the influence of structure parameters on the crystallization of porphyrins and derivatives.

Voids calculations in packing

Voids were calculated and visualized in order to show the importance of solvents molecules in the packing of unit cells. The figure 7 shows voids of two structures from the figure 6a-d, in which (a) belongs to the first group and (d) to the third group.

Figure 7: 3D visualization of voids on the packing.

As it can be seen in the figure 7, the packing of porphyrins and derivatives occur in creating voids that could be covered by solvents molecules used during crystallization. The above results confirm what were shown from the results of packing characteristics of unit cells. By the way, high packing of porphyrins and derivatives structures are obtained when $R \leq 5\%$, while low packing when $R > 5\%$. This confirms the influence of structure on the crystallization of porphyrins and derivatives. Therefore, $R \leq 5\%$ was considered as defined criterion in order to assess parameters of structure.

Parameters of structure analysis

The results from the analysis of the remaining parameters of structure are summarizing in the following flow chart of the figure 7. From the 5794 structures of porphyrins and derivatives, have fixed the refinement factor to $R \leq 5\%$. The influences of the substitutions as well as the presence of metal in the cavity of the porphyrins nucleus are analysed, in order to evaluate the importance of structures deformation in the unit cells.

We can notice that the big sample was refined to the one where the structures were solved with a high accurate. So, a set of 1502 structures compose that sample or 26% of the overall samples. The analysis of 26% of structures with $R \leq 5\%$ shows that 16% of substitution of porphyrins occurs in meso position, 4% in β position and 6% in meso- β position. In the set of 16% of porphyrins substituted at the meso position, 14% have metal atom as atomic central and 2% do not. For the total of 14% of porphyrins substituted at the meso position and having metal, 3% have iron as metallic atom and within this group 2% has Fe(II). These results indicate that the substituted and metallated porphyrins in meso positions occur with an important number of structures which have very good refinement parameters. As showed a few amount of meso substituted porphyrins having iron

as metal were crystallized. This results shows the importance of the conformational or deformation changing that increases the packing of unit cells and leading to an optimal crystallization.

Figure 7: Analysis of parameters of structure of porphyrins

For the meso substituted porphyrins unit cells are more packed than the ones β substituted and short length Van Der Waals bonds are formed between porphyrins packing the same unit cells and the bonds length are shorter than Van Der Waals radius of binding atoms (figure 8a-b-c). In the two cases solvents molecules stabilize the crystalline building and porphyrins and derivatives bind through those solvents molecules (figure 8b-c-d). A study on the 3D structure resolution of meso porphyrin by x-ray diffraction on single crystals reported the establishment of weak C-H...O hydrogen bond between oxygenated solvents molecules and porphyrins network in the crystal [33].

Figure 8: 3D visualisation of the compacity of meso substituted porphyrins.

The below structure of the figure 9 shows the molecular structures deformation. It can be see that deformation occurs thanks to the substitutes around porphyrins (figure 10) in meso position. A study on the planarity of crystals structures of Zn-porphyrins reported that introduction of extremely bulky groups at the meso positions alone leads to porphyrins with considerably altered chemistry, and on the basis of their spectroscopic characteristics inferred a distorted macrocyclic conformation [34].

Figure 10: 3D visualisation of structure deformation of a porphyrin due to a meso substitution.

Distances between nitrogen atoms as described in the figure 11 were calculated to show the deformation of the cavity occupy by the metal.

Figure 11: Distances between Nitrogens.

The found mean values of distances between nitrogens are $N^4-N^{19} = 4.064 \pm 0.103 \text{ \AA}$ and $N^7-N^{21} = 4.054 \pm 0.095 \text{ \AA}$. The theoretical value of the distance between nitrogen atoms found in literature is 4.2 \AA . Compared to the two calculated value, we can see that the presence of metal in the central cavity of porphyrins reduces a little the distances between nitrogen atoms. These results show that may be the contraction of the central cavity of porphyrins together with the substitution that could lead to the deformation of macrocycle porphyrins and derivatives.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this work was to analysis the structural factors that could lead to an optimal crystallization of porphyrins and derivatives. The results shows that most of the structures of porphyrins determined from stable single crystals are those conformations were deformed by the substitution of the macrocycle and by the occupation of the central cavity by a metal atom. The detailed analysis of quantitative geometric parameters such and coordination as well as voids are in process.

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